

Studies in the isoFlavone Series.

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Consideration of the various evidences available as regards the chemical nature of cyanomaclurin led Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 721) to the formulation of a possible flavan structure for it, *viz.*,

Among the attempts which have been made to settle the constitution of cyanomaclurin, mention may be made of the researches of Bhalla and Ray (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 288); Appel and Robiuson, (*ibid.*, 1935, 752), Mitter and Saha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 257) who considered the possibility of flavanone structure, but they could not establish this structure by a complete synthesis.

Within recent years a good number of isoflavones have been found to occur among plant products pertaining to both the tinctorial and non-tinctorial varieties, and it occurred to us that the possibility of an isoflavone structure for cyanomaclurin was worthy of consideration.

The formula ($C_{15}H_{10}O_6$) agrees fairly closely with the molecular formula of cyanomaclurin as determined by Perkin ($C_{15}H_{12}O_6$) and it also accounts for the fission products of the substance.

We, therefore, took up the synthesis of a substance of the above constitution, which even if it failed to give synthetic cyanomaclurin itself, would definitely exclude its isoflavone structure.

We started (*vide Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1935, p. 153) from β -resorcyaldehyde dimethylether which was obtained in good yield from resorcinol dimethylether according to the method of Adams and Montgomery (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 1518), later improved in

our laboratory by Mitter and Saha (*loc. cit.*). We found, however, that the yield of the aldehyde could be still further improved by decomposing the imino-chloride first with ice and then with ice-cold hydrochloric acid in small quantities, for otherwise a considerable portion of the aldehyde is converted into tarry products. From the aldehyde the azlactone (I) was prepared which was hydrolysed into the corresponding pyruvic acid (II). This was converted into the nitrile (IV) over the oxime (III).

The nitrile was condensed with phloroglucinol by the method of Hoesch (*Ber.*, 1915, **48**, 1122) to give 2':4'-dimethoxyphenyl-2 : 4 : 6-trimethoxyacetophenone (V).

Attempts of conversion of the substance into the corresponding isoflavone by the method of Spüth and Lederer (*Ber.*, 1930, **63**, 743) as modified by Venkataraman and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 513, 1770) having failed, the corresponding 2-methylisoflavone was prepared by the Allan-Robinson method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 2192).

The isoflavone (VI) dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with a pinkish colouration. It gave with ferric chloride a transient violet colour which changes to dark brown after some time. On warming with dilute caustic soda solution no blue colouration was produced.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Azlactone of β -Resorcyaldehyde Dimethylether (I).—It was prepared according to the method of Kropp and Decker (*Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 1186). β -Resorcyaldehyde dimethylether (16 g.), hippuric acid (17.5 g.) and fused sodium acetate (8 g.) were powdered to an intimate mixture and heated with 30 c.c. of acetic anhydride for 1 hour when the contents of the flask set to a fine deep yellow crystalline mass. A few c.c. of alcohol were added to the mixture while still warm and the contents triturated in a mortar. The thick paste was filtered at the pump and after washing successively with water, alcohol and benzoi, recrystallised from alcohol or glacial acetic acid as yellow needles, m.p. 168°; yield 17.5 g. (Found: N, 4.52. $C_{18}H_{15}O_4N$ requires N, 4.53 per cent).

2 : 4-Dimethoxyphenylpyruvic Acid (II).—The azlactone (10 g.) dissolved in 50 c.c. of 10% caustic soda solution was refluxed over a free flame for 4 hours. The solution, after cooling, was saturated with sulphur dioxide till the separation of benzoic acid was complete which was filtered after 24 hours. After crystallising twice from glacial acetic acid, it was obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 156°, which turned into a red sticky mass on exposure to air, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 59.05; H, 5.38. $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 58.92; H, 5.36 per cent).

The oxime.—The pyruvic acid (10 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (8 g.) and 8% caustic soda solution (100 c.c.) were warmed to 50° for a few minutes and allowed to stand overnight. On acidification the oxime separated. It was crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum ether, m. p. 145° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.97. $C_{11}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 5.86 per cent).

2 : 4-Dimethoxyphenylacetonitrile (IV).—The dry oxime (10 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (6 c.c.) on the water-bath and after the vigorous reaction had subsided (2-3 minutes), about 50 c.c. of water were added and the mixture shaken vigorously. The nitrile separated first as an oil, which soon solidified. On washing it with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallising it from rectified spirit, it was obtained as beautiful needles, m. p. 76°, yield 6 g. (Found: N, 8.01. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 7.9 per cent).

2' : 4'-Dimethoxyphenyl-2 : 4 : 6-trihydroxyacetophenone (V).—Dry HCl gas was passed into an ice-cold ethereal solution of the dry

nitrile (2 g.) and anhydrous phloroglucinol (2 g.) in 25 c.c. of ether containing freshly fused anhydrous zinc chloride (0.8 g.) until saturation. On keeping overnight, reddish orange crystals separated which were washed with ether and boiled about half an hour with 75 c.c. of water. On cooling the aqueous solution, colourless crystalline plates separated, which after recrystallisation melted at 175°. (Found : C, 63.24 ; H, 5.28. $C_{16}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 63.15 ; H, 5.26 per cent).

The *dibenzyl* derivative, prepared by heating the ketone (3 g.), benzyl chloride (3 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3.6 g.) in dry acetone (45 c.c.) for 12 hours, separated as colourless needles from a mixture of alcohol and acetic acid, m.p. 135°, yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 74.43 ; H, 5.9. $C_{30}H_{28}O_8$ requires C, 74.38 ; H, 5.8 per cent).

All attempts at condensation of the product with ethyl formate in presence of molecular sodium failed.

5 : 7-Diacetoxy-2' : 4'-dimethoxy-2-methylisoflavone.— The dry ketone (1 g.), fused sodium acetate (1 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) were refluxed on an oil-bath at 175°-180° for 12 hours. The cold reaction product was treated with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid when oily drops separated, which solidified on keeping overnight. It was filtered, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) as colourless sandy crystals, m.p. 204°-205°. (Found : C, 63.97 ; H, 4.84. $C_{22}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 64.07 ; H, 4.85 per cent).

5 : 7-Dihydroxy-2' : 4'-dimethoxy-2-methylisoflavone (VI).— The acetylated isoflavone (1 g.), dissolved in a few c.c. of 1% alcoholic potash, was warmed on the water-bath for 30-45 minutes. On acidification, a flocculent mass was obtained which crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) as colourless sandy crystals, m. p. 213°-14°, yield 0.4 g. The isoflavone exhibited no fluorescence in aqueous alkali. (Found : C, 65.70 ; H, 4.76. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 65.85 ; H, 4.87 per cent).